

Reactive Methylene Compounds. Part VI. Condensations with Benzenediazonium Salts

H. G. Garg*

Several 4-substituted dibenzoylmethanes have been coupled with benzenediazonium salts to furnish the corresponding benzeneazo-4-substituted dibenzoylmethanes.

In continuation of the previous work (Garg *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 626) the coupling of benzenediazonium chlorides with 4-substituted dibenzoylmethanes, such as, 4-chloro-(I: X = Cl), 4-methyl-(I: X = Me), 4-bromo-(I: X = Br), 4-nitro-(I: X = NO₂) dibenzoylmethanes, has now been studied.

The so-called benzeneazo derivatives obtained are highly coloured, crystalline solids, and are soluble in ethanol, benzene, acetic acid, etc. These develop red colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and are precipitated as such on dilution.

EXPERIMENTAL**

The syntheses of 4-chloro-, 4-bromo-, 4-methyl- and 4-nitro- dibenzoylmethanes were easily effected by the action of sodium methoxide on dibromides of substituted benzylideneacetophenones (Bodforss, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 214; Barnes and Dodson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1585).

Benzeneazo-4-chlorodibenzoylmethane.—Aniline (0.05*M*) was diazotised in the usual manner; the filtered diazonium chloride solution was run into a cooled, stirred mixture of crystalline sodium acetate (50 g.) and 4-chlorodibenzoylmethane (0.05*M*) in ethanol (100 c.c.). Benzeneazo-4-chlorodibenzoylmethane separated immediately and was collected after 10 hours. It was recrystallised from acetic acid. Different derivatives are described in Table I.

Benzeneazo-4-bromodibenzoylmethanes (Table I), benzeneazo-4-methyldibenzoylmethanes (Table II), and benzeneazo-4-nitrodibenzoylmethanes (Table II) were similarly prepared.

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* Present address: Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

** Melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE I

No.	Substituted benzene derivative.	4-Chlorodibenzoylmethane.			4-Bromodibenzoylmethane.		
		Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.
1.	Benzenezo-	86%	130°	Yellow	89%	153	Golden yellow
2.	4-Methoxy-	84	148°	Canary-yellow	86	189	Orange
3.	4-Bromo-	90	163°	Yellow	92	205°	Golden yellow
4.	4-Chloro-	89	186°	Canary-yellow	91	202°	Yellow
5.	3-Chloro-	89	168°	Golden yellow	91	160°	Orange
6.	2-Chloro-	..	..	..	90	154°	Dirty yellow
7.	4-Nitro-	94	221°	Yellow	95	196°	Golden yellow
8.	3-Nitro-	92	170°	Light yellow	94	159°	Pale yellow
9.	4-Methyl-	84	168°	Yellow	86	186°	Yellow
10.	3-Methyl-	84	169°	Light yellow	86	151	Orange
11.	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	92	198°	Canary-yellow	91	212°	Pale yellow
12.	2-Nitro-4-chloro-	91	182°	Yellow	91	180°	Yellow

Formula.

Formula.

Yield. M.P. Colour.

%Halogen. Found. Calc.

Formula.

Yield. M.P. Colour.

%Halogen. Found. Calc.

Formula.

TABLE II

*No.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	4-Methyl-dibenzoylmethane.			4-Nitro-dibenzoylmethane.		
				Formula.	Found.	Calc.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.
1.	87%	123°	Yellow	$C_{21}H_{19}O_2N_4$	Ni: 7.92%	8.18%	..	..	..
2.	85	124°	Pale yellow	$C_{23}H_{20}O_2N_4$	N: 7.32	7.52	83%	175	Yellow-orange
3.	90	153°	Golden yellow	$C_{19}H_{17}O_2N_2Br$	Br: 18.81	19.00	89	205°	Yellow
4.	89	152°	Yellow	$C_{25}H_{17}O_2N_4Cl$	Cl: 9.13	9.42	88	214°	Do.
5.	89	140°	Golden yellow	$C_{23}H_{17}O_2N_4Cl$	Cl: 9.11	9.42	87	182	Pale yellow
6.	..	..	..	..	..	..	86	193	Yellow
7.	94	168°	Yellow	$C_{23}H_{17}O_2N_4$	N: 10.62	10.85	..	..	..
8.	93	162°	Do.	$C_{25}H_{17}O_2N_4$	N: 10.71	10.85	..	..	..
9.	85	156°	Golden yellow	$C_{23}H_{19}O_2N_4$	N: 7.62	7.86	..	..	..
10.	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
11.	91	182°	Pale yellow	$C_{25}H_{16}O_2N_4Cl$	Cl: 8.12	8.42	..	..	Yellow
12.	90	180°	Golden yellow	$C_{25}H_{16}O_2N_4Cl$	Cl: 8.21	8.42	88	> 250°	..

* The number of benzenezo derivatives corresponds to those listed in Table I.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
MERRITT COLLEGE, MERRITT.

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